

POLICY BRIEF

PATHWAYS TOWARD CLIMATE-RESILIENT FISHERIES IN BRAZIL

FOREWORD

The ocean sustains life on Earth, providing food and livelihoods for billions of people. Yet it is also changing faster than at any other time in human history. Rising temperatures, shifting currents, and the increasing frequency of extreme weather events are transforming marine ecosystems and the lives of those who depend on them. For countries like Brazil – where millions of families rely directly or indirectly on fishing – these changes are not distant forecasts. They are realities already being felt in coastal and riverine communities across the nation.

Fishing is one of humanity's oldest food systems, and one of the most essential. It provides high-quality protein with a low carbon footprint and supports jobs, cultures, and economies across Brazil's vast coastline and inland waters. Ensuring that fishing continues to play this vital role requires management that is both scientifically grounded and socially inclusive – management that recognizes the growing pressures of a changing climate and prepares fisheries to adapt to them.

This policy brief was developed with the purpose of guiding public managers in identifying the priority actions needed to make Brazil's fisheries more resilient and prepared for the challenges that climate change will bring. It outlines practical and achievable measures – strengthening data collection, improving stock assessments, fostering adaptive management, ensuring participatory decision-making, protecting essential

habitats, and promoting regional cooperation between countries. Together, these actions offer a roadmap toward a future in which fisheries continue to provide food, employment, and dignity, without compromising the health of our oceans.

Many of the challenges identified here – and reflected in the priority actions proposed – are deeply connected to the institutional instability that has long affected fisheries administration in Brazil and to the fragility of its current legal framework. Building long-lasting and structural changes will depend not only on better governance but also on a comprehensive reform of the Fisheries Law. The ongoing debate around Bill 4789/2024 represents a critical opportunity to modernize this framework, providing greater stability, transparency, and accountability. Its discussion, improvement, and eventual approval should be supported by all sectors of Brazilian society – but especially by public managers, who hold the responsibility of transforming policy into progress.

At Oceana, we believe that the solutions to climate change in the ocean are also solutions for people. By investing in transparency, science, and inclusion, Brazil can transform its fisheries into a model of sustainability and resilience. The task ahead is urgent, but it is also full of opportunities to ensure that fishing remains a source of life and prosperity for generations to come.

Ademilson Zamboni

Vice-President of Oceana in Brazil

OVERVIEW

The planet's rapidly changing climate presents humanity with unprecedented challenges. Global temperatures are rising each year, and the oceans — absorbing most of the sun's energy — are becoming progressively warmer. The melting of polar ice is expected to alter ocean currents, while rainfall patterns are shifting, and natural events are becoming more intense and frequent. Across the globe, societies are already experiencing the effects of these transformations in their daily lives, economies, and forms of social and political organization [1]. Humanity is now confronted with a climate system that no longer behaves as it once did.

Global challenges such as eradicating poverty, reducing hunger, generating employment and income, and pursuing equality and social justice, are increasingly embedded within a context that demands new approaches. These solutions must now evolve within the dual framework of mitigating anthropogenic causes of climate emergency and adapting to its consequences. Long-term strategies based on fossil fuel dependence are no longer viable, nor can hunger and poverty be addressed through deforestation or degradation of freshwater systems [2].

Fishing plays a strategic role in this global scenario and in achieving the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. It represents a vital food system that generates employment, income, and highly nutritious food. Among all forms of animal protein production, fisheries account for only about 4% of total greenhouse gas emissions [3]. Compared to beef and poultry production, global fisheries generally generate fewer greenhouse gases and contribute less to eutrophication and acidification [4].

According to the latest data from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), global fisheries produce around 90 million tons annually, the result of the direct labor of 34 million people — most of them engaged in small-scale and artisanal fishing, which accounts for roughly 40% of global production [5].

Nearly 90% of all fish caught are destined for human consumption, providing essential micronutrients that underpin food security and human health, especially in developing countries [5]. While 93% of terrestrial animal protein comes from beef, pork, and poultry, fisheries contribute with more than 2,300 species consumed worldwide [6]. In Brazil, hundreds of species of fish, crustaceans, and mollusks, are caught and consumed — mostly in regions with the lowest human development indexes — enriching diets with diverse and valuable nutrients.

However, overfishing, habitat degradation, and biodiversity loss remain major trade-offs of fishing activity. Mitigating these impacts while maximizing fisheries' benefits depends on effective management systems — science-based, with transparent and participatory governance and oversight.

With most of its coastline influenced by warm, nutrient-poor tropical waters, Brazil's extractive fishing sector is modest compared to neighboring countries such as Peru, Chile, and even Argentina. The most recent report from Brazil's Fisheries Authority — published in 2025 after a 15-year gap in official data — estimate national capture fisheries production at approximately 470 thousand tons per year [7]. Yet, significant information gaps persist, especially along the North and Northeast coasts, suggesting that actual production is likely higher.

Inland fisheries face an even more critical scenario. Despite encompassing some of the world's largest river basins, Brazil's freshwater fisheries potential remains poorly understood, hindered by a near-total absence of monitoring and reliable data on production or fishers' numbers. The report cites a freshwater fisheries production of only 570 tons in 2024 – compared to 240 thousand tons in 2009 [7].

Even if underestimated in global terms, fisheries hold immense socioeconomic importance in Brazil. Approximately two million fishers are formally registered, and an estimated ten million people rely on the activity, directly or indirectly. Thousands of traditional fishing communities along coasts and rivers sustain cultural heritage and local knowledge while defending territories increasingly pressured by sectors such as tourism, energy, infrastructure, and even by urban expansion.

Nevertheless, weak fisheries governance continues to drive stock depletion and ecosystem degradation, notably through destructive practices such as bottom trawling. These internal vulnerabilities are compounded by additional climate-induced risks [8]. The expansion of warm-water belts toward the poles – a process known as tropicalization – is shifting the distribution of species more commonly associated with cold waters to temperate and polar regions. In Southern Brazil, this may result in the loss of valuable fishery resources migrating into the Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) of Uruguay and Argentina, reducing opportunities for both artisanal and industrial fleets [9]. Prolonged El Niño events have also been linked to stock collapses – such as sardines, which accounted for over 20% of Brazil's total catch in 2024 [7]. Crises in fish availability drive fleets to seek alternative resources, intensifying conflicts and the overfishing of stocks already under considerable pressure.

Shifts in rainfall patterns – with historically severe droughts and floods occurring in shorter intervals – are affecting inland and coastal fisheries, placing hundreds of thousands of fishers in vulnerable conditions. Recent events, such as the floods in the State of Rio Grande do Sul and the Amazon droughts in 2024, have severely impacted artisanal fishers. In the latter case, for example, these fishing communities had to be supported through emergency assistance from the government of nearly one billion reais (approximately 185.37 million US dollars, in the average rate exchange for 2024) [8].

Even before the climate crisis, effective fisheries management was vital to ensuring sustainable food production. Today, as fish stocks, ecosystems, and communities face accelerated environmental pressures, governance quality will determine whether fisheries adapt or collapse. Most Brazilian fisheries remain regulated by outdated,

static rules that fail to account for natural fluctuations in fishing productivity. Without systematic monitoring, prediction, and adaptive management, the sector will be poorly equipped to face the challenges ahead.

Addressing the intersection between fisheries and climate change in Brazil thus means confronting unprecedented environmental and institutional challenges. Governments, civil society, and the fishing sector must collaborate to understand present conditions and plan for the future of fisheries while simultaneously addressing instability, scarce data, and fragile governance.

In response to this reality, this report outlines a set of strategic priority actions, aimed at strengthening the resilience of fisheries and fishing communities and ensuring the sustainable production of food in a changing climate scenario.

01

Credit: Agência Brasil/Fernando Frazão

CONTINUOUS DATA COLLECTION

OVERVIEW

Access to consistent and reliable fisheries data is a prerequisite for effective management, providing the technical foundation to develop a portfolio of adaptation strategies. Comprehensive information on total catches, species composition, fleet size, fishing effort, gear types, fishing areas, and the economic value of fisheries is essential for informed decision-making and long-term sustainability.

RELEVANCE

When fisheries data are collected continuously, with adequate spatial and temporal resolution, and made publicly accessible, they serve as the foundation for science-based governance.

Reliable datasets allow managers to estimate fish stock biomass and fishing mortality with greater accuracy, analyze fleet dynamics and patterns of fishing effort, and design adaptive management plans. They also make it possible to assess the socioeconomic impacts associated with environmental variability and extreme events, helping anticipate and mitigate risks to fishing-dependent communities. Furthermore, continuous monitoring enables the construction of risk scenarios and vulnerability maps, which are essential tools for planning climate adaptation strategies.

CURRENT CONTEXT IN BRAZIL

Brazil has made notable progress in fisheries monitoring, data transparency, and public access to information. However, significant gaps remain, particularly in data-poor regions, notably in inland fisher-

ies and marine small-scale fisheries in the North and Northeast regions. There is also uncertainty regarding the sustainability of recent progress in data collection and dissemination, as well as concerns about institutional stability and the long-term funding of monitoring and research programs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To strengthen the resilience to climate change, the National Fisheries Authority should:

- I. Expand monitoring coverage in regions facing significant data scarcity, particularly inland and coastal fisheries in the North and Northeast regions;
- II. Establish and formalize partnerships with public and private institutions engaged in projects of fisheries monitoring and data collection;
- III. Develop and maintain institutional infrastructure capable of receiving, integrating, standardizing, and disseminating fisheries data;
- IV. Assign binding institutional responsibility to the Fisheries Authority for the nationwide coordination and implementation of ongoing fisheries monitoring and reporting programs.

02

Credit: Oceana/Christian Braga

STOCK ASSESSMENT AND POPULATION DYNAMICS MONITORING

OVERVIEW

The population dynamics of many fish stocks are expected to be strongly affected by environmental changes. Reproductive processes, growth, recruitment, and natural mortality rates are likely to experience both acute and chronic alterations. As a result, productive potentials and biological reference points, such as Maximum Sustainable Yields (MSY), will also shift – with some stocks showing reduced productivity, while others may find more favorable conditions and emerge as new fishing opportunities.

RELEVANCE

Monitoring these population variations through regular stock assessments is essential to support the implementation of science-based regulations that maintain fish stocks within biologically safe limits and establish catch and effort levels compatible with their productive capacity. Tracking indicators of stock dynamics also enables the anticipation of crises related to stock collapses, low catches, or scarcity events, as well as the identification of opportunities arising from environmentally driven increases in abundance.

CURRENT CONTEXT IN BRAZIL

In Brazil, stock assessments have been conducted sporadically, inconsistently, and without integration into a coherent long-term management framework. The systematic use of stock assessments to define catch limits and management measures has been implemented only within the past decade, but the scenario is still far from the ideal [8].

The situation is particularly critical for inland fisheries resources and for sardines and other small pelagic species. In freshwater systems, there are no historical records of stock assessments, and filling these gaps in the short term is unlikely due to the scarcity of basic data. For small pelagic species, given their high economic and social importance, stock monitoring should be treated as a priority – especially considering the strong influence of environmental and oceanographic variability on their population dynamics. Most of these stocks, however, have never been properly assessed in Brazil.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To strengthen the resilience to climate change, the National Fisheries Authority should:

- I. Establish a National Stock Assessment Program, providing the legal, technical, and operational framework for conducting and integrating stock assessments into fisheries management;
- II. Regularly assess key fish stocks of high socioeconomic importance, as well as those in critical conservation status;
- III. Focus assessment efforts on under-studied fisheries and sectors, including small pelagics and inland fisheries, to address major knowledge gaps and improve management foundations.

03

Credit: Oceana/Christian Braga

ADAPTIVE FISHERIES MANAGEMENT

OVERVIEW

Environmental changes in aquatic systems generate both biological and social impacts on fisheries. For example, fluctuations in the abundance of fishery resources and more frequent collapses of certain stocks are expected to occur over shorter time intervals. Similarly, extreme climatic events can directly affect traditional fishing communities and fleets. Management models capable of anticipating such crises and providing rapid, evidence-based responses will become increasingly necessary.

ment tools in the Brazilian regulatory framework include seasonal closures, fleet size limitations, and spatial fishing restrictions.

While these measures serve important purposes, they do not inherently promote feedback mechanisms or regular reassessment. As a result, once implemented, such rules tend to remain in force for decades without systematic review. This rigidity leaves Brazilian fisheries poorly equipped to respond to increasingly frequent crises or new fishing opportunities.

RELEVANCE

Adaptive management is based on predefined decision rules linked to conceptual objectives and quantitative indicators. When continuously monitored by fisheries managers, these mechanisms allow for timely adjustments to control measures — such as catch limits and fishing efforts — based on observed changes in stock or environmental conditions.

This dynamic approach is essential to ensure that fisheries, particularly those most influenced by environmental variability, remain capable of adjusting to periods of scarcity and abundance. In doing so, adaptive management helps to optimize socioeconomic benefits while minimizing environmental risks and maintaining sustainability across different climatic and ecological scenarios.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To strengthen the resilience to climate change, the National Fisheries Authority should:

- I. Invest in the development of management plans tailored to the scale and characteristics of each fishery, incorporating climate variables and scenario analysis for stocks and fleets;
- II. Establish catch control rules linked to measurable indicators and objectives, enabling rapid adjustments;
- III. Prioritize regulatory mechanisms that promote feedback and regular updates to scientific information used in management;
- IV. Introduce legal provisions establishing maximum validity periods for management regulations, thereby encouraging regular review and adaptation.

CURRENT CONTEXT IN BRAZIL

Fisheries management in Brazil remains largely characterized by outdated, static, and fragmented regulatory instruments, often lacking alignment with clear management objectives for each fishery. The dominant manage-

04

Credit: Oceana/Christian Braga

SOCIAL PARTICIPATION IN DECISION-MAKING

OVERVIEW

Participatory management is a cornerstone of effective and equitable fisheries governance. Engaging those who directly depend on fisheries for their livelihoods strengthens management systems by incorporating local knowledge, aligning conservation measures with socioeconomic realities, and fostering shared responsibility in resource management. This inclusive approach improves both environmental outcomes and the resilience of fishing-dependent communities.

RELEVANCE

Participatory management enhances social resilience, enabling faster and better-informed responses to environmental and economic changes. Through the active involvement of stakeholders in developing management plans, control rules, and evaluation mechanisms, fisheries governance becomes more adaptive and context-sensitive.

Collaborative structures such as co-management councils, community advisory groups, and multi-stakeholder forums provide the foundation for transparent dialogue and shared decision-making. When effectively implemented, these mechanisms strengthen trust between institutions and communities, improve participatory data collection, and foster a sense of co-ownership in the management process.

CURRENT CONTEXT IN BRAZIL

Fisheries governance in Brazil remains largely centralized and top-down, with limited and uneven participation of fishing communities in management processes. Historically, the forums designated for social partic-

ipation — Fisheries Management Councils — have operated in an unstable and intermittent manner, undermining continuity and institutional trust.

Although the legal framework allows for stakeholder participation through these councils, their centralized structure tends to favor discussions and decisions focused on large-scale industrial fisheries, making it difficult for small-scale and artisanal communities to propose and legitimize locally adapted solutions. This rigidity restricts innovation and responsiveness at the community level. Addressing this challenge requires the creation of decentralized participatory mechanisms capable of ensuring representativeness and legal recognition of local management arrangements.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To strengthen the resilience to climate change, the National Fisheries Authority should:

- I. Promote a stable and institutionalized mechanism regarding Fisheries Management Councils, ensuring continuity, transparency, and genuine social participation across all regions;
- II. Establish decentralized mechanisms that enable communities to develop and formalize locally tailored management rules and agreements;
- III. Integrate co-management approaches combining scientific with traditional and local knowledge;
- IV. Provide technical and financial support to regional and local councils, enhancing their operational capacity and representativeness.

05

Credit: Agência Brasil/Fernando Frazão

PROTECTING ESSENTIAL HABITATS

OVERVIEW

Essential habitats such as coral reefs, mangroves, sea-grass beds, estuaries, and riverine systems, are the ecological foundation of fisheries. They sustain the productivity, recruitment, and survival of numerous fish species throughout their life cycles. Beyond their role in supporting fisheries, many of these habitats and ecosystems are also critical for protecting coastlines and the homes of millions of people, buffering against erosion, storms, and sea-level rise. However, these habitats are increasingly threatened by destructive fishing practices and a wide range of non-fishing pressures, including coastal development, pollution, and climate-driven changes in temperature and ocean biogeochemistry. Safeguarding these ecosystems is indispensable for maintaining fishery productivity, biodiversity, coastal protection, and the long-term sustainability of food systems derived from capture fisheries.

RELEVANCE

Protecting essential habitats contributes directly to ecosystem resilience and fishery sustainability. Healthy and preserved spawning and nursery grounds, benthic structures, and water quality, ensure the ecological functions that support stock renewal and productivity. Moreover, habitat conservation buffers the impacts of climate change by sustaining carbon sequestration, shoreline protection, and biodiversity. Integrating habitat protection into fisheries governance reduces vulnerability to environmental degradation while enhancing the adaptive capacity of fishing-dependent communities.

CURRENT CONTEXT IN BRAZIL

In Brazil, essential habitats face growing pressures from both fishing and non-fishing activities. Destructive

gears such as bottom trawls continue to degrade seabed habitats, while pollution from rivers severely affects coastal and estuarine systems. Coral reefs are increasingly stressed by warming waters and unregulated tourism, leading to bleaching and biodiversity loss. Mangroves, vital as breeding and nursery grounds, are being rapidly converted for shrimp farming, urban expansion, and port infrastructure, compromising their ecological and socio-economic functions. Despite the recognized importance of these ecosystems, current policies and management instruments remain fragmented and insufficiently integrated into fisheries governance frameworks.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To strengthen the resilience to climate change, the National Fisheries Authority should:

- I. Implement effective management and control of fisheries with the greatest potential to damage marine and freshwater habitats — particularly bottom trawling — by adopting spatial restrictions and gear modifications;
- II. Protect critical habitats essential to fish life cycles, including spawning and nursery areas, through integrated planning that combines fisheries management and habitat conservation;
- III. Expand and strategically design protected areas to safeguard ecosystem services and biodiversity while supporting sustainable fisheries and community livelihoods.

06

Credit: Oceana/Christian Braga

REGIONAL COOPERATION BETWEEN COUNTRIES

OVERVIEW

Climate change is reshaping marine ecosystems and altering the spatial distribution of fish stocks across national boundaries. As ocean temperatures rise, species traditionally abundant in Brazilian waters may shift their ranges beyond the country's Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ), leading to potential losses in fishing opportunities. This process of tropicalization, driven by warming seas, is expected to be particularly pronounced in Brazil's Southern region, where several cold-water species of economic importance to both artisanal and industrial fisheries may decline in occurrence or abundance. These changes call for strengthened regional and international cooperation to ensure sustainable management of shared and straddling fish stocks.

RELEVANCE

Regional cooperation between countries plays a pivotal role in addressing the transboundary nature of climate impacts on fisheries. Shared monitoring systems, data exchange, and joint scientific assessments are essential for understanding how stocks migrate and how their productivity evolves under changing environmental conditions. Bilateral or multilateral agreements can provide mechanisms for shared governance and fair allocation of fishing opportunities, preventing conflicts and ensuring that straddling fish stocks continue to contribute to food security, livelihoods, and regional economic stability. Coordinated action at the regional level is also vital to harmonize management measures, reduce overfishing risks, and promote a collective transition toward climate-resilient fisheries.

CURRENT CONTEXT IN BRAZIL

Brazil has traditionally managed its fisheries within national boundaries, with limited engagement in coop-

erative mechanisms beyond multilateral commitments under organizations such as the FAO or the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (ICCAT). However, as species distributions shift, maintaining this inward approach will constrain Brazil's ability to respond effectively. The Southern fisheries, where cold-water species such as certain demersal and pelagic stocks are likely to move into neighboring EEZs, are particularly vulnerable. Strengthening cooperation with adjacent coastal nations – notably Uruguay and Argentina – will be essential for improving the understanding of stock dynamics, preventing disputes over access, and establishing mutually beneficial management arrangements.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To strengthen the resilience to climate change, the National Fisheries Authority should:

- I. Promote regional cooperation between countries for data and information exchange, focusing on environmental monitoring, stock distribution, and fleet activity;
- II. Conduct joint assessments and management of transboundary and migratory species shared with neighboring countries to align conservation and exploitation objectives;
- III. Establish bilateral and regional dialogues aimed at identifying shared fishing opportunities and establishing cooperative frameworks that promote sustainable and equitable fisheries in a changing ocean.

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